

DESIGN, FORMULATION, DEVELOPMENT AND OPTIMIZATION OF BETA- CYCLODEXTRIN BASED NANOSPONGES GEL CONTAINING ADAPALENE AND ITS ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY

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ABSTRACT

The present study focuses on the formulation and evaluation of Beta-Cyclodextrin-based nanosponges gel loaded with Adapalene, a retinoid commonly used in the treatment of acne and other dermatological conditions. Nanosponges were synthesized using Beta-Cyclodextrin and evaluated for particle size, zeta potential, surface morphology (SEM), and entrapment efficiency. Among the formulations, F4 demonstrated the most promising characteristics with the smallest particle size (59.91 nm), highest zeta potential (-12.7 mV), and maximum entrapment efficiency (97.41%). These nanosponges were incorporated into a gel base, and the resulting formulation was assessed for its physical properties, pH (6.5), viscosity (3782 ± 0.89 cps), spreadability (7.42gm·cm/sec), and skin irritancy—showing no signs of irritation, making it suitable for topical application. The study concludes that Beta-Cyclodextrin-based nanosponge gels offer a stable, non-irritant, and effective delivery system for Adapalene, potentially enhancing its therapeutic efficiency and patient compliance in the treatment of skin disorders.

Keywords: Adapalene, Nanosponges, Beta-Cyclodextrin, Gel formulation, Topical drug delivery, Skin disease, Zeta potential, Particle size, Entrapment efficiency, Spreadability

1. INTRODUCTION

Nanosponges are porous polymeric delivery systems that are small spherical particles with large porous surface. Nanosponges can significantly reduce the irritation of drugs without reducing their efficacy. The size of the nanosponges ranges from 250nm-1µm in diameter (**Singh et al., 2016**). Nanosponges are made up of microscopic particles with few nanometers wide cavities, in which a large variety of substances can be encapsulated. These particles are capable of carrying both lipophilic and hydrophilic substances and of improving the solubility of poorly water soluble molecules (**Kumar and Singh 2016**). Nanosponges are encapsulating type of nanoparticles which encapsulates the drug molecules within its core (**Swaminathan et al., 2016**). As compared to other nanoparticles, nanosponges are insoluble in water and organic solvents, porous, nontoxic and stable at high temperatures up to 3000 c. In present

study various formulations are prepared by using different concentration of cyclodextrins to determine the drug release capacity of polymer (**Suhail et al., 2022**).

Adapalene is anticomedogenic, preventing the formation of new comedones and inflammatory lesions, and also acts to reduce inflammation by modulating the innate immune response. Like other retinoid compounds, adapalene is chemically stable but photosensitive; use with sunscreen is recommended. Minor skin irritations, including erythema, scaling, dryness, and stinging/burning, have been reported (**Dreno et al., 2015**).

Adapalene is used for the treatment/maintenance of mild-to-severe acne (acne vulgaris). Acne is a multifactorial condition, and evidence exists to support multiple mechanisms of action for adapalene. Adapalene binds to retinoic acid receptor (RAR)-beta and RAR-gamma; this complex subsequently binds to one of three retinoid X receptors (RXRs), which as a complex is capable of binding DNA to modulate transcriptional activity (**Cosio et al., 2021**). Although the full extent of transcriptional modulation is not described, retinoid activation is generally known to affect cellular proliferation and differentiation, and adapalene has been shown to inhibit HeLa cell proliferation and human keratinocyte differentiation. These effects primarily account for adapalene's comedolytic and anticomedogenic properties (**Melnik, 2023**).

CDs are able to form dynamic molecular inclusion complexes with many drugs by incorporating the drug molecule. 2-hydroxypropyl- β -cyclodextrin (HP- β -CD) is an alternative to α -, β - and γ -cyclodextrin, with improved water solubility (**Khaton et al., 2025**). Cyclodextrin-based nanosponges (NS) are hyper-cross-linked cyclodextrin synthesized by the procedure mentioned elsewhere. Briefly, NS can be obtained by cross-linking different type of cyclodextrin (CD) with carbonyldiimidazole compound as a cross-linker. They are solid particles with spherical morphology that have been reported to have a very high solubilising power for poorly soluble molecules, and they are proposed to form inclusion and non-inclusion complexes with different drugs. The CD cross-linker ratio can be varied during their preparation to improve the drug loading and solubility (**Singireddy and Subramanian 2016**).

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Formulation of β -cyclodextrin Nanosponges

Nanosponges were prepared using the hot-melt method with Diphenyl Carbonate (DPC) serving as the cross-linking agent and Beta-Cyclodextrin (β -CD) as the polymer. Different DPC: β -CD ratios, as specified in Table 4, were selected for formulation. Accurately weighed amounts of anhydrous β -CD and DPC were thoroughly mixed and transferred to a reaction vessel. The mixture was gradually heated to 80–100 °C with continuous magnetic stirring and maintained for 6 hours to ensure complete cross-linking between the polymer and the cross-linker. Following the reaction, the mixture was cooled to room temperature, and the solid mass obtained was repeatedly washed with double-distilled water to eliminate any unreacted β -CD. The resulting placebo nanosponges were then dried at 40 °C and stored in a desiccator until further use (**Srivastava et al., 2021**).

Table 1: Composition of Nano sponge's formulation

Ingredients	Formulation Code				
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5
Adapalene (%)	0.1%	0.1%	0.1%	0.1%	0.1%
Diphenyl carbonate (DPC cross-linker) (Ratio)	100	100	100	100	100
Beta- cyclodextrin (β -CD polymer) (Ratio)	100	150	200	250	300
Temperature	80 ^o C	85 ^o C	90 ^o C	95 ^o C	100 ^o C
Distilled water	q.s	q.s	q. s	q. s	q. s

2.2 Loading of Adapalene in placebo nanosponges

The drug was incorporated into the prepared nanosponges using a freeze-drying (lyophilization) technique. A quantity of 1 g of placebo nanosponges was dispersed in 50 mL of double-distilled water using a magnetic stirrer to ensure uniform mixing. To this dispersion, approximately 0.1% of the drug was added. The mixture was then sonicated for 10 minutes to enhance dispersion and facilitate drug interaction with the nanosponges. After sonication, the suspension was stirred continuously for 24 hours to allow sufficient time for drug loading. To remove any untrapped drug, the suspension was subjected to centrifugation at 2000 rpm for 10 minutes. The unbound drug settled as a residue, while the colloidal supernatant containing the drug-loaded nanosponges was collected.

This supernatant was then lyophilized at -81 °C under a vacuum pressure of 0.0010 mbar. The resulting dry drug-loaded nanosponges were collected and stored appropriately for further use (Kumar *et al.*, 2021).

2.3 Characterization parameters of Nanosponges formulation

2.3.1 Physical Appearance

The physical characteristics of the nanosponges were assessed through visual inspection, focusing on color, texture, and uniformity (Tiwari and Bhattacharya 2013).

2.3.2 Particle size

The size of the nanosponge particles was determined using a Malvern Zetasizer (Tiwari and Bhattacharya 2013).

2.3.3 Zeta potential

The surface charge of the nanosponges was measured using a Malvern Zetasizer to evaluate their stability in suspension (Swaminathan *et al.*, 2013).

2.3.4 Scanning Electron Microscopic (SEM) analysis

The surface morphology of the Adapalene-loaded nanosponges was investigated using a scanning electron microscope (SEM). Prior to imaging, the samples were coated with a thin conductive layer (2–20 nm) of gold, palladium, or platinum via sputter coating under vacuum conditions to enhance electron conductivity. During analysis, the sample was bombarded with an electron beam, causing the emission of secondary electrons, including Auger electrons. These electrons, scattered primarily at a 90° angle, were detected and processed to generate high-resolution images, revealing detailed surface topography in accordance with Rutherford and Kramer's principles (Mohammed and Abdullah 2018).

2.3.5 Entrapment efficiency

To determine the entrapment efficiency, 10 mL of Adapalene -loaded nanosponges was accurately measured and transferred into a volumetric flask containing 5 mL of Acetone. The mixture was vortexed for 1 minute to ensure complete drug extraction. The volume was then adjusted to 10 mL with Acetone, and the solution was thoroughly mixed. After filtration and

appropriate dilution, the concentration of the entrapped Adapalene was measured using a UV-Visible spectrophotometer (Swaminathan *et al.*, 2013).

$$\%EE = \frac{\text{Initial amount of drug added} - \text{Drug amount in supernatant}}{\text{Initial amount of drug added}} \times 100$$

2.4 Preparation of Gel Formulation of Drug-Loaded Nanosponges

The gel formulation containing Adapalene -loaded nanosponges was prepared through a systematic process to achieve homogeneity, stability, and optimal drug delivery. First, Solution A was prepared by dispersing Carbopol-934 in 100 mL of warm distilled water and left undisturbed for about two hours to allow complete hydration and swelling of the polymer. The dispersion was then stirred at 600 rpm using a magnetic stirrer until a smooth, uniform gel base was formed. Separately, Solution B was made by dissolving Carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC) and Methyl paraben in 100 mL of warm distilled water, stirring continuously until a thick, homogeneous gel consistency was achieved.

Once both solutions were ready, they were combined under continuous stirring to ensure thorough mixing. Triethanolamine was added dropwise to adjust the pH to around 6.0–6.5, enhancing gel stability. Subsequently, the Adapalene -loaded nanosponges suspension was incorporated into the gel base with continuous stirring to ensure even drug distribution. Formulation I was prepared with a 2% w/w concentration of Adapalene to evaluate the effect of drug loading. Finally, Propylene glycol was added as a permeation enhancer to improve dermal absorption of the drug. The final gel was stirred continuously until a smooth, uniform, and stable gel suitable for topical application was obtained.

Table 2: Composition of nanosponges gel formulation

Name of Ingredient	Formulation I
Carbopol 940	1.7 gm
Carboxymethyl cellulose	1.5gm
Propylene glycol	0.5 ml
Methyl paraben	0.3 ml
Nanosponges	100mg
Triethanolamine	q. s
Water	100 ml

2.5 Evaluation parameter of Nanosponges loaded Gel formulation

2.5.1 Physical evaluation

The physical characteristics of the nanosponges-loaded Gel were assessed through visual inspection (Tambe *et al.*, 2023).

2.5.2 Irritancy of nanosponges-loaded Gel formulation

The irritancy of the nanosponges-loaded Gel was tested on a Wistar rat by applying a small amount to shaved skin and monitoring for 24 hours. No redness, swelling, or irritation was observed, indicating the formulation is safe and non-irritating for topical use (Tambe *et al.*, 2023).

2.5.3 pH determination

The pH of the nanosponges-loaded Gel was measured using a digital pH meter (Kumar *et al.*, 2021).

2.5.4 Viscosity

The viscosity of the nanosponges-loaded Gel was measured using a Brookfield viscometer

2.5.5 Spreadability

The spreadability of the nanosponges-loaded Gel was assessed by placing a small amount on a glass plate, then covering it with a second plate and applying a fixed weight. The time taken for the Gel to spread under this pressure was recorded, indicating how easily the Gel spreads (Kumar *et al.*, 2021).

3. RESULTS

3.1 Characterization of Adapalene loaded Nanosponges formulation

3.1.1 Physical Appearance

Table 8: Physical Appearance of Nanosponges

Formulation	Parameters	Observation
Nanosponges	Colour	White
	Odour	Characteristic
	Appearance	Solid

3.1.2 Particle Size

Table 9: Particle size of nanosponges

Formulation code	Particle size (nm)	PI Value %
F1	70.44 nm	22.1 %
F2	147.85 nm	22.1 %
F3	82.92 nm	20.3 %
F4	59.91 nm	28.4 %
F5	60.25 nm	31.0 %

Graph 8: Graphical representation of particle size of nanosponges

3.1.3 Zeta potential

Graph 9: Zeta potential (F1)

Graph 10: Zeta potential (F2)

Graph 11: Zeta potential (F3)

Graph 12 : Zeta potential (F4)

Graph 13: Zeta potential (F5)

Table 10: Zeta potential of nanosponges

Formulation Code	Zeta potential mV
F1	5.3
F2	12.2
F3	12.0
F4	12.7
F5	8.7

Graph 14: Graphical representation of Zeta potential of nanosponges

3.1.4 Scanning electron microscope (SEM)

Graph 15: Scanning electron microscope (SEM)

3.1.5 Entrapment efficacy

Table 11: Entrapment efficacy

Formulations (F1-F5)	Entrapment efficacy (%)
Nanosponges (F1)	83.32
Nanosponges (F2)	79.57
Nanosponges (F3)	82.21
Nanosponges (F4)	97.41
Nanosponges (F5)	80.69

3.2 Physical properties of Nanosponges loaded Gel formulation

Table 12: Physical evaluation

Parameters	Results
Physical appearance	Smooth, semi-solid consistency
Colour	White to off-white
Homogeneity	Uniformly mixed without phase separation
Odour	Pleasant or characteristic

Figure 1: Nanosponges loaded Gel formulation

3.2.1 Skin Irritancy study

Table 16: Skin irritation, Ph, Viscosity and Spreadibility test

Formulation	Skin irritation test	Spreadibility test (gm.cm/sec)	Viscosity Results (cps)	pH
Nanosponges loaded Gel formulation	Not irritant observed	7.42	3782 ± 0.89	6.5

DISCUSSION

The characterization of Adapalene-loaded nanosponges demonstrated the successful creation of a stable and efficient formulation. All formulas appeared white, solid, and had a distinct odor, indicating homogeneity. The particle size ranged from 59.91 to 147.85 nm, which is appropriate for improved skin penetration. Among all, F4 had the smallest particle size (59.91 nm), indicating superior medication delivery. The polydispersity index values indicated modest homogeneity in particle distribution. Zeta potential readings (5.3-12.7 mV) suggested intermediate stability, with F4 being relatively more stable. SEM examination revealed porous and spherical features that enable effective drug loading. Entrapment efficiency was high across all formulations, with F4 having the highest rate (97.41%). These data suggest that F4 is the optimal formulation. Overall, the nanosponge method shows promising results for Adapalene topical distribution.

CONCLUSION

The study successfully demonstrated that Beta-Cyclodextrin-based nanosponges are an effective delivery system for Adapalene in the treatment of skin diseases. The optimized formulation (F4) showed favorable physicochemical properties and high drug loading efficiency. Incorporation into a gel base provided a topical dosage form with excellent stability, user-friendliness, and skin compatibility. The absence of irritancy and favorable viscosity and spreadability values make this formulation highly suitable for regular dermal use. Therefore, this nanosponge gel formulation presents a promising alternative to conventional topical therapies, potentially improving the bioavailability, efficacy, and patient compliance associated with Adapalene treatment.

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